

Supplementary Material 4. EEG Granger Connectivity Analysis at Baseline and During the Socially Evaluated Cold Pressor Test (SECPT)

Table S3 presents EEG Granger causality (GC) connectivity metrics as delta differences ($GCA = SECPT - Baseline$) relative to a 5-minute resting baseline. GC analysis quantifies the extent to which the activity in one brain region statistically predicts activity in another, providing a directional measure of functional connectivity. Connectivity measures included global connectivity, nodal connectivity, and pairwise directional GC values. Global connectivity refers to the average GC strength across all electrode pairs and represents the overall magnitude of directional information flow within the predefined frontoparietal electrode montage. Nodal connectivity was assessed through three indices: in-strength, the sum of all incoming GC connections to a given electrode, reflecting the amount of information it receives from the network; out-strength, the sum of all outgoing GC connections from a given electrode, indicating the amount of information it sends to the network; and causal flow, calculated as the difference between out-strength and in-strength, which determines whether a node functions more as a net sender (positive values) or receiver (negative values) of information. Pairwise directional GC values represent the GC strength for each specific source→target electrode pair, providing fine-grained detail about the direction and magnitude of connectivity between cortical sites.

At the global level, GC strength decreased from baseline to SECPT ($\Delta = -0.0133$), suggesting an overall reduction in brain-wide directional connectivity under acute psychosocial stress. In other words, acute stress reduced the efficiency or magnitude of information being transferred across the frontoparietal network. At the nodal level, all cortical sites showed small reductions in both in-strength and out-strength during SECPT. The most pronounced decreases were observed at parietal (P3, P4) and central (C3, C4) electrodes,

indicating reduced information exchange in posterior and sensorimotor regions during stress. Frontal electrodes (F3, F4) also decreased slightly in strength. Causal flow values were close to zero for all electrodes; however, changes revealed a clear pattern, with most sites showing slightly more positive values, indicating a shift toward weaker net outflow (greater net inflow) during stress. By contrast, P3 and P4 showed negative values, which reflect a relative shift toward net outflow. However, because posterior→target pairwise edges decreased, this pattern indicates a reduction, not an increase, in posterior driving.

At the pairwise level, most directional connections weakened during SECPT, particularly central-parietal (e.g., C3→P3, C4→P4) and parietal-central (e.g., P4→C3, P3→C3) pathways, as well as several posterior–posterior interactions (e.g., P3→P4, P4→P3). However, some connections showed slight increases, including F3→C4, C4→F3, C3→F4, F4→C4, and C4→F4, suggesting that stress effects on directional connectivity were region-specific rather than uniform. Overall, these findings suggest that acute psychosocial stress induced by the SECPT is associated with a global reduction in directional EEG connectivity, most notably affecting posterior cortical regions and central-parietal pathways, with limited areas of increased activity on frontal-central connections. In other words, psychosocial stress appears to prompt a reallocation of connectivity, reducing widespread information exchange while selectively preserving or strengthening pathways within the frontoparietal network that support executive-control–relevant processing and adaptive responding. This pattern suggests a stress-induced reorganization of cortical communication, characterized by reduced global integration alongside the targeted maintenance of regionally specific connections.

TABLE S3 EEG Granger Connectivity Metrics Across Baseline and SECPT.

	Variable	Δ	SE
Global			
	Global Strength	-0.0133736743403026	0.00908
Nodal			
In-Strength	F3	-0.000514828913281573	0.00129
	F4	-0.0000898569995532842	0.00137
	C3	-0.00354870133410017	0.00215
	C4	-0.0011655448442655	0.00156
	P3	-0.00329623564861643	0.00178
	P4	-0.0047585066004856	0.00264
Out-Strength	F3	-0.000802337489007798	0.00119
	F4	-0.000665984442122929	0.00095
	C3	-0.00379967436721088	0.00223
	C4	-0.00195487636706709	0.00196
	P3	-0.00273876907019392	0.00184
	P4	-0.00341203260469995	0.00268
Casual Flow	F3	-0.000287508575726221	0.00095
	F4	-0.000576127442569643	0.00081
	C3	-0.000250973033110716	0.00056
	C4	-0.000789331522801583	0.00064
	P3	0.000557466578422505	0.00068
	P4	0.00134647399578566	0.00081
Pairwise	Source→Target		
	F3→C3	-0.000000143657580742026	0.00025

F3→C4	0.000274417011153997	0.00024
F3→F4	-0.000154284821184743	0.00014
F3→P3	-0.00061337822946641	0.00047
F3→P4	-0.000308947791929899	0.00045
F4→C3	0.000094319650267294	0.00021
F4→C4	0.000157485155714017	0.00029
F4→F3	-0.000193624018982345	0.00012
F4→P3	-0.000312005540614872	0.00024
F4→P4	-0.000412159688507022	0.00039
C3→C4	-0.000109572040951492	0.00012
C3→F3	-0.0000863419434035041	0.00038
C3→F4	0.000156670323842678	0.00029
C3→P3	-0.00198050764167324	0.00110
C3→P4	-0.00177992306502533	0.00096
C4→C3	-0.0000763055981449841	0.00012
C4→F3	0.000162687800468168	0.00031
C4→F4	0.0000216485424023782	0.00052
C4→P3	-0.000184302791186774	0.00045
C4→P4	-0.00187860432060587	0.00133
P3→C3	-0.00195974642980311	0.00113
P3→C4	-0.0000409030362052283	0.00039
P3→F3	-0.000337629951938993	0.00039
P3→F4	-0.0000216179178291087	0.00034
P3→P4	-0.000378871734417477	0.00030
P4→C3	-0.00160682529883862	0.00099

P4→C4	-0.0014469719339768	0.00122
P4→F3	-0.0000599207994249022	0.00042
P4→F4	-0.0000922731267844877	0.00042
P4→P3	-0.000206041445675132	0.00035

Note: Δ = Delta Difference (SECPT – Baseline); SE = Standard Error; GC: Granger

Causality.